

HIRSHFELD SURFACE ANALYSIS OF THE CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF THE COMPLEX COMPOUND OF Cu (II) NITRATE BASED ON THE 2,5-DI (METHYLTHIO) -1,3,4-THIADIAZOLE LIGAND

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Relevance: Currently, the Hirshfeld surface analysis method is widely used to identify intermolecular interactions in the crystal structure of compounds and to study their impact on the stability of the crystal lattice. The theoretical data obtained through this method are yielding good results in studying the practical properties of crystals. Therefore, investigating the structure of this complex using this method is one of the urgent scientific issues of the research.

Research objective: To quantitatively and qualitatively determine the molecular interactions of the copper nitrate complex $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ formed with the ligand 2,5-di (methylthio) -1,3,4-thiadiazole (L) using Hirshfeld surface analysis of its crystal structure.

Methods and techniques: Hirshfeld surface analysis was conducted using the Crystal Explorer 17.5 program to visualize the intermolecular interactions in the crystal structure. Two-dimensional fingerprint plots were calculated as part of this analysis.

On the Hirshfeld surface, points with low impact are colored blue, while colors ranging from green to red indicate points with high impact.

For the $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ molecule, the Hirshfeld surface d_{norm} was calculated using standard high surface precision (Figure 1).

Figure 1. (a) Hirshfeld surface of the $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ complex according to d_{norm} and (b) two-dimensional fingerprint areas indicating the percentage contributions of all interactions.

According to the results of the analysis of two-dimensional fingerprint region drawings, it was established that the interactions $\text{O}\cdots\text{H}/\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ (31.4%), $\text{S}\cdots\text{H}/\text{N}\cdots\text{S}$ (19.7%), $\text{H}\cdots\text{H}$ (11%), make the largest contribution to the Hirshfeld surface.

Result: The largest share of the total surface L is represented on the fingerprint map as edged wings with 31.4% share of total interactions of $\text{O}\cdots\text{H}/\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ interactions formed as a result of the interaction of hydrogen atoms in the methyl group with oxygen atoms of neighboring molecules. The greatest contribution of the influence of $\text{O}\cdots\text{H}/\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ on the Hirshfeld surface is explained by the abundance of intermolecular and intramolecular hydrogen bonds. Also, the contribution of the effects $\text{S}\cdots\text{O}/\text{O}\cdots\text{S}$ (3.9%) and $\text{N}\cdots\text{H}/\text{H}\cdots\text{N}$ (3.5%) shows a smaller share (Fig2).

Figure 2. The interaction distances of individual atoms in the crystal structure of the $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ complex (two-dimensional fingerprint areas and their relative ratio at the Hirschfeld surface) were studied.

Conclusion: It was found that the area of fingerprints in the $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ complex has the highest interactions $\text{O}\cdots\text{H}/\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ (31.4%). This affects the stability of the crystalline arrangement of the molecular structure.